

Making sense of a new national context in comparative housing: personal and systemic reflections of a researcher's journey in France

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Keywords: comparative housing policies, housing studies

1. Introduction

Considering the complex meshing behind housing systems, the fact that housing policies are highly contextual is not particularly ground-breaking. Variegated political and institutional pathways, economic conditions, the state of the housing stock, or simply socio-culturally constructed housing aspirations each singularly shape the ways housing systems function so as to—in an ideal world—provide decent homes for all. This complexity leads to a particular set of challenges for comparative housing researchers.

For example, anyone discussing ‘social housing’ across national boundaries needs to account for the wide variation in the meaning of the term, which may refer to very different objects in different countries (Scanlon et al., 2014). It could refer solely to publicly owned units offered as a last resort option for the most vulnerable (like in the United States), while it may also refer to a broad tenure type geared at a range of household types by a wide variety of actors, whether public, not for profit or collective (such as in Sweden or Singapore). In fact, even the previous sentences are oversimplifications, as only a—relatively—lengthy discussion of national specificities of different cases studied allows to create a space for comparison and differentiation (Haffner et al., 2009). In fact, defining and building understandings are central pieces of most comparative housing literature publications.

Yet, this relatively well acknowledged difficulty hides a wider conceptual issue; the words underpinning these definitions and differentiations, somewhat obscure the actual process leading researchers to make sense of the various logics, institutions and actor behaviours operating within a specific housing system. In fact, where the literature is quite explicit on the multiple variations across contexts and what they mean for comparative work, there is little interest given to the actual learning process, how individual researchers acquire the knowledge necessary to carry research on housing, whether at home or abroad. Ultimately, this poses a challenge for comparative work specifically: how can one effectively understand the national specificities of an ‘external’ housing system to an extent that would allow them to carry meaningful comparative work?

Stemming as a reflection on Van Heur’s (2020) call to better integrate personal histories and the role of researchers’ positionality in affecting the knowledge they produce; this contribution will reflect on both the personal and systemic aspects involved in the process of “learning” a new housing system. This, with a more specific aim to encourage comparative researchers working on policies, institutions, and actors to better engage openly and reflectively with their topics.

2. Research work

This contribution will be articulated around the personal experience of the author in “learning” the French and Dutch housing systems along with a broader reflection on the systemic implications behind the housing as an object of knowledge acquisition. Firstly, the presentation will trace the trajectory of the author as a Canadian slowly specializing on housing policy research while moving between different countries. It will serve as an example of the different conceptual and practical challenges that one can encounter in the process. This experience will be framed as a form of knowledge acquisition bearing important similarities with that of learning a second language: from the acquisition of a new vocabulary, to using a different grammar, to interpret a new reality.

Following up on the parallels with didactics, the second part of the presentation will delve more systematically into the “learning” of housing research through an analysis of the syllabi and reading lists used in different housing studies classes in North America and Europe. This analysis will study the different themes, topics and objectives of these courses in order to compare the similarities and dissimilarities in the ways the topic of housing is introduced to bachelor’s and master’s students in the fields of public policy and urban planning. The analysis will show that while crosscutting themes are plentiful, they are most often underpinned by a specific syntax anchored in local realities. It will also posit that vocabulary and topics that may seem connected can easily turn into false friends, where a foreign concept appears deceptively similar to another in one’s own frame of reference. On the surface, this situation raises questions on the transferability of knowledge acquired in such classes: are these local specificities only used as examples to present more general processes, or are they so particular to a given context that they need to be specified? More deeply, this situation should also lead us to reflect more openly on the impact of our own positionality in our work. Indeed, if these courses introduce housing to students using a specific local syntax, one can reasonably wonder in what ways this originally localized exposure (also in informal settings) later shapes the way we approach our object of research. Pursuing the analogy with language, this question has important similarities to those surrounding linguistic relativity as to “whether people who speak different languages think differently” (Wolff & Holmes, 2011, p. 253).

3. Conclusion

This contribution argues that there is a clear need to explicitly reflect on the impact of our own individual experiences in the way we carry out our research on housing, especially in comparative work. Doing so could not only improve our capacity to deal with shortcomings in dealing with unfamiliar contexts, but also represents an exciting opportunity to introspectively explore the relationship we have with our research object. Ultimately, this presentation aims to present possible avenues offered by a reflexive exploration of the interface between the initial housing experiences of researchers, system-specific idiosyncrasies and the resulting production of knowledge.

Acknowledgment

This contribution has been carried as part of the RE-DWELL project, which received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956082.

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